

Phenol Formaldehyde Cationic Matrices Substituted by Coal from Assam Mines

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The sulfonated Assam Coal, which by itself acts as an exchanger was used to replace the polymeric matrix of phenol formaldehyde cation exchanger, varying the substituent content from 0 to 100%. All the important characteristics of the composites have been determined. It is observed that the substitution upto 30-40% is economical, since the composites obtained retain all the essential properties compared to the unsubstituted phenolic cationite.

SYNTHESIS and study of ion-exchangers is of interest because of their largescale use particularly in the softening of water. Since the current popular exchangers owe their origin to petroleum products, there is a continual increase in the cost of these exchangers.

There is a greater need now either to find out altogether newer resins which are economical compared to the existing exchangers or to identify substitutes which can partly replace the polymeric content of the existing exchangers to a considerable extent while the properties of the parent resin are retained. The impact of substitution will be more if the substituent itself acts as an exchanger. Earlier work done by the present authors revealed that coke¹, sawdust^{2,3} and lignite⁴ could be substituted upto 30-40% in phenolic cationites. The substitution did not have any adverse effect and in addition the composites obtained were macroporous⁵.

The present work deals with the preparation and study of the properties of sulfonated phenolics, substituted partially by sulfonated coals obtained from Assam Coal Mines⁺.

Experimental

Materials and Reagents.

Coal from Assam Coal Mines; Phenol (BDH Reagent); Conc. sulfuric acid (Sp. Gr. 182); Formaldehyde (BDH Reagent).

(i) Preparation of the samples :

Phenol (300g) and sulfuric acid (365 ml) were mixed and heated to ~100° on a water bath for two hours, cooled immediately in the ice and kept overnight. Assam coal samples of 25, 50, 75 and 100 g. were sulfonated with 50, 100, 150 and 200 ml of conc. sulfuric acid by heating on a water bath for four hours. The samples were mixed with 135 ml of phenol sulfonic acid so as to keep the percentage substitution of Assam coal respectively at 30, 45, 60 and 65. Each mixture was polymerised with 55 ml of 37% formaldehyde solution at 70°, ground, sieved and preserved for further work. These constitute the samples labelled AP I to AP IV. A separate sample of Assam coal was sulfonated and subjected to studies as such. The amounts of reagents used and the yields of samples are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—AMOUNTS OF REAGENTS USED AND YIELDS OF THE COMPOSITES

sample	Phenol Sulfonic acid, ml	Assam Coal g	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ ml	Formalin ml	Yield g	Assam coal in resin%
Unsubstituted resin	135	0	0	55	70	0
AP-I	135	25	50	55	110	20-25
AP-II	135	50	100	55	165	30
AP-III	135	75	150	55	180	40-45
AP-IV	135	100	200	55	240	40-45
Sulf. Assam Coal	0	100	100	0	120	10 0

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⁺In revising this paper the referee has brought out that Assam coal could be treated with anthracene oil for a limited time period followed by sulfonation as done by the C.F.R.I.

(ii) *Physical Measurements :*

Swelling measurements were made by allowing the samples to equilibrate in water overnight. The wet weight was taken as M_w and the corresponding dry weight M_d was obtained after drying the same lot at 70° and then exposing to air. The gravimetric percent swelling, α , was measured from the equation

$$\alpha = \frac{M_w - M_d}{M_d} \times 100$$

Particle size was determined by sieving the samples in the sieves of 500, 300, 150 and 108μ

Exchange capacity measurements were made by the method followed by Kunin⁷. The samples were converted into H^+ -form by washing with HCl followed by distilled water to remove acidity. Known weight of wet samples in the H^+ -form were equilibrated with standardised solutions of Na^+ (0.1M), Mg^{2+} (0.04M), and Ca^{2+} (0.04M). The following exchange occurred :

where M^+ represents a metal ion.

The dry weight content of the samples equilibrated were determined by drying a part of the wet sample at 70° and weighing it. The exchange between H^+ in the resin and Na^+ in the solution was determined by titrating the supernatant against standard NaOH solution since there is an increase in the H^+ concentration of the supernatant due to the exchange. Exchange between Ca^{2+}/Mg^{2+} in the supernatant and H^+ in the resin were determined by titrating against standard NaOH as well as EDTA. The latter measures the decrease in Ca^{2+}/Mg^{2+} concentration in the supernatant.

The total amount of Ca^{2+}/Mg^{2+} in the resin after exchange was separately estimated as follows., The known weight of the resin in Mg^{2+} -form was repeatedly washed with 100 ml of water till no trace of Mg^{2+} was there in the filtrate. The total Mg^{2+} thus extracted

was estimated by EDTA titration. Subsequent to washing with water, the resin was eluted with 100 ml portions of HCl till no more Mg^{2+} was extracted. Once again in the filtrate, the amount of Mg^{2+} was estimated by EDTA titration. The exchange capacity of big cations like $(NR_4)^+$ where R is methyl, ethyl or butyl was also determined as above from the pH change in the supernatant after equilibration with known amounts of the resin.

The surface areas of the samples were measured by PNP adsorption⁸. A standard solution of PNP in benzene (7g/lt) was prepared. 0.25-2 ml portions were dried and dissolved with several aliquots of water containing small amounts of NaOH. The absorbance of the solutions were measured at 400 nm. A calibration curve was thus prepared. For adsorption measurements, one gram of the dry resin was treated with 10 ml of PNP in benzene. The supernatant was treated as above and from the calibration curves the amount of PNP adsorbed was determined. The surface area was estimated from the PNP adsorbed, taking the PNP molecular occupancy to be 52.5\AA^2 .

Attrition stability of the samples of the composites were compared with that of unsubstituted resin as follows. Both types of sample were initially sieved to give batches containing particles greater than 500μ in size. These were then swollen in water and shaken continuously for six hours. Samples were separated by filtration, dried and weighed. Subsequently these were sieved on a 500μ mesh size and amounts of the substance passing through the holes were weighed

Results and Discussion

The percent composition and physical characteristics of the exchangers are given in Table 1. The particle sizes are in the range of 500μ - 106μ . The average percent swelling decreases from 100% resin to AP IV. Table 2 gives the data on attrition stability. As seen from columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, samples before shaking are made up of basically particles above 500μ in size and less than 2-3% of the particles of small size. After shaking for 6 hours and repeating the sieving process

TABLE 2—ATTRITION EFFECT ON THE EXCHANGERS

Sample	Wt. of resin the taken, g	Before shaking		After shaking			
		Amount passed through 500μ mesh g	Amount remained, %	Amount passed through 500μ mesh g	Amount remained %	Amount remained g	
Unsubstituted resin	28.56	0.14	0.49	28.42	0.93	3.26	27.52
AP-I	19.29	0.08	0.41	19.21	0.41	2.1	18.88
AP-II	26.88	0.09	0.33	26.79	0.52	1.99	25.50
AP-III	20.95	0.33	1.57	20.62	0.39	1.93	19.80
AP-IV	27.88	0.21	0.75	27.68	0.30	1.09	27.05

it is observed that the percentage of particles less than 500 μ in size formed due to attritional breaking during sieving is less than 2-3%. Also this is the same for the pure resin and the composites AP I to AP IV. Thus not much difference is seen in the attritional stability between the pure and the composite although in the latter it is possible that the resin might have formed in the capillaries of coal particles.

The apparent capacity for the exchange of Na⁺ (0.1M) and Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺ (0.04M) on the H⁺-form of the exchangers and big cations NR₄⁺ (0.04M) are listed in Table 3. As expected the exchange capacities are higher for the divalent ion as compared to Na⁺ at the same concentration. Two interesting features may be noted. For any given ion, the capacity as determined by pH titration for AP-II containing 30% coal and AP-III containing 45% coal are comparable to that of pure resin. Sulfonated Assam coal itself has capacities of 0.6-0.8 meq/g. Fig. 1 is a plot of exchange capacity vs coal content in the resin. It is seen that though there is

continuous decrease in capacity of coal the fall is not much up to 30-40%. This indicates that substitution of coal up to this extent is economical since the capacity of the composite is comparable with that of the unsubstituted resin.

Secondly, the capacities as determined by EDTA titrations for Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺ are found to be higher than those obtained by pH titrations. This may be because the composite has considerable adsorption and binds some additional Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺ by adsorption besides ion-exchange. While the pH titration will measure the hydrogen ions released by exchange, EDTA titrations give the total Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺ which has been taken up by any method of binding including ion-exchange.

To check on the strength with which Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺ ions are bound in the matrix, the resin was completely converted into Mg²⁺-form and extracted with water subsequently. The results are shown in Table 4, As

TABLE 3—CAPACITIES OF H⁺-FORM OF THE COMPOSITES

Sample	Average swelling %	Exchange capacity in meq/g estimated by					
		Na ⁺ (0.1 M) pH	Mg ²⁺ (0.04 M) pH	Mg ²⁺ (0.04 M) EDTA	Ca ²⁺ (0.04 M) pH	Ca ²⁺ (0.04 M) EDTA	(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ N ⁺ (0.04 M) pH
Unsubstituted resin	200	1.82	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	—
AP-I	190	1.60	1.70	4.42	1.75	4.5	1.60
AP-II	135	1.58	1.6	4.00	1.65	2.6	1.55
AP-III	130	1.42	1.55	4.3	1.75	4.37	1.56
AP-IV	70	1.20	1.55	2.00	1.56	2.50	1.47
Sulf. Assam Coal	120	0.63	0.9	1.00	0.6	0.82	—

Fig. 1. Capacity VS percentage of coal in the exchanger. O: [Ca²⁺] = 0.04 M; □: [Mg²⁺] = 0.04 M

TABLE 4—SORPTION/ION EXCHANGE PROPERTIES OF THE ION EXCHANGERS

Sample	Total amount of Mg ²⁺ form of resin taken, g (dry weight)	Mg ²⁺ eluted by water washing, meq.	Total Mg ²⁺ eluted by subsequent HCL washing, meq.	Capacity, meq./g	
				Adsorbed Mg ²⁺	Exchanged Mg ²⁺
Substituted resin	2.73	1.58	4.60	0.56	1.68
AP-II	2.74	1.26	4.12	0.50	1.5
AP-III	3.17	2.21	7.54	0.70	2.37

seen from the data, out of the total Mg²⁺ bound by the resin, some amount gets eluted by water itself indicating that the binding is loose and is probably held by adsorption. However, by HCl elution it is seen that the more

strongly bound or exchanged Mg^{2+} is always greater than 1.5-1.8 meq/g. This is close to the value from pH titration. Thus, it seems that the composites can definitely bind up to 1.8 meq/g by exchange. Over and above this, there may be some additional adsorption. Further measurements on column capacity underway would determine the optimal useful capacity.

TABLE 5—SURFACE AREAS OF THE COMPOSITES.

Sample	Surface area, m ² /g
Unsubstituted resin	231
AP-I	100
AP-II	80
AP-III	76
AP-IV	60

In fact, the PNP-adsorption data (Table 5) indicate that the composites are porous. The surface area is of the order of 100 m²/g. Thus, the samples combine ion-exchange capacity with adsorptive power. Also as shown in Table 2 the percent swelling in water is not high as compared to conventional gel type ion-exchangers indicating a certain rigidity in the matrix. Thus, these resins may prove useful where they are required to stand large osmotic shock. Since they have inherent porosity, the resins may be useful in non-aqueous

solvents. As a result of porosity it is seen that even for the exchange of big ions of the type $(NR_4)^+$ the resins show their full capacity (cf. Table 2 last column) and are thus likely to be useful in the pharmaceutical industry.

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